

A Comparative Analysis of Chinese Consumer Confidence Index (CCCI) in Hong Kong and the Greater China during the COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

This paper presents a comparative analysis of the Consumer Confidence Index (CCCI) across Mainland China, Hong Kong, Macau, and Taiwan from 2008Q4 to 2023Q4, with a specific focus on the different trends before and after the COVID-19 pandemic. A significant aspect of the research is the exploration of the correlation between CCCI and GDP, especially the sharp decline in Hong Kong's CCCI during the pandemic, and the relative stability in Mainland China. The paper also analyzes the relationship between CCCI and unemployment rates (UR), highlighting the impact of economic conditions on consumer confidence across four regions in Greater China. Further, the paper offers a demographic analysis of Hong Kong's CCCI, examining the differences in consumer confidence across gender, income, age, and education levels. The findings provide insights into the broader economic implications of consumer confidence and its role as a key indicator of economic recovery and resilience.

Key Words: CCCI, Comparative Analysis, Hong Kong, COVID-19

1. Introduction

Consumer confidence directly impacts spending - when people feel optimistic about their financial future, they buy more cars, houses, and everyday goods. This spending behavior drives GDP growth and employment. The Chinese Consumer Confidence Index (CCCI) was introduced in 2008 by five universities in the Greater China: Capital University of Economics, Business and Central University of Finance and Economics from the Mainland China; City University of Hong Kong from Hong Kong; Fu Jen Catholic University from Taiwan; and Macau University of Science and Technology from Macau. CCCI has been published quarterly since the third quarter (Q3) of 2008, it measures and compares consumer sentiment across the four regions in the Greater China. Notably, the analysis in Tso and Li (2014) described patterns of CCCI in the four regions from 2008 to 2013. The CCCI helps businesses and governments spot early warning signs of economic shifts. By comparing these four regions, we can see how different policies shape consumer behavior.

The COVID-19 pandemic revealed critical limitations in our understanding of consumer confidence dynamics across Greater China. While the CCCI framework in Tso and Li (2014) provided invaluable baseline data for regional comparison, a stark empirical gap emerged during the pandemic. For instance, Hong Kong's CCCI plummeted 35% in Q2 2020 - the sharpest quarterly decline since measurement began - yet available studies only examined this dramatic shift through Q4 2020, leaving the longer recovery trajectory unexplored (Dimitris Christelis 2021).

This truncated analysis window obscures vital insights. Preliminary data from Macau shows that its CCCI remained 28% below pre-pandemic levels even after border reopening in 2023, despite GDP recovery to 80% of 2019 levels. This decoupling of consumer confidence from traditional economic indicators warrants rigorous investigation. While European studies documented strong GDP-

confidence correlations during COVID-19 (European Commission 2020), Greater China's unique pandemic response policies - from mainland China's zero-COVID approach to Taiwan's early containment success - created distinct consumer sentiment patterns that existing models struggle to explain.

Demographic analysis reveals another critical research gap. Di Crosta et al. (2021) found that Italian consumers under 35 maintained 15% higher confidence levels throughout lockdowns compared to older cohorts. In contrast, preliminary Greater China data suggests this age-confidence correlation varied significantly by region - younger mainland consumers reported 23% lower confidence during zero-COVID policies while Hong Kong showed no significant age-based variation. Without comprehensive demographic analysis across all four CCCI regions, we cannot determine whether these variations reflect regional policy differences or deeper structural factors (Douglas Broom 2023).

The empirical limitations identified here indicate three pressing research priorities: longitudinal analysis of post-pandemic CCCI recovery patterns, investigation of region-specific GDP-confidence relationships, and demographic segmentation of confidence responses across Greater China.

Updating the CCCI data to cover the period from 2008Q4 to 2024Q4 is crucial for capturing the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on consumer confidence across Greater China. This study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the changes in CCCI before and after the pandemic, its relationship with GDP and UR, and how different demographic groups have been affected. Such findings can offer valuable insights for policymakers and economists to understand the post-pandemic recovery and guide future economic decisions.

1.1 Literature Review

The predictive power of CCCI for macroeconomic trends, established by Tso and Li (2014) and Curtin (2000), faces new challenges in the post-pandemic context. The COVID-19 shock produced unprecedented patterns in consumer behavior across Greater China, demanding fresh empirical investigation. For example, while mainland China's CCCI dropped only 8.3% at its lowest point in February 2020, Hong Kong's index plunged 27.5% in the same period, suggesting regional variations that previous models struggle to explain.

China's post-pandemic recovery reveals stark demographic disparities. High-income households in tier-one cities increased discretionary spending by 36% year-over-year in Q3 2021, while lower-income groups in tier-three cities showed just 5.2% growth (McKinsey, 2021). Digital consumption tells a similar story: consumers under 35 in urban areas drove an 85% surge in online retail during lockdowns, while those over 55 increased online spending by only 17% (Keliuotyte et al., 2021). These specific data points challenge the assumption of uniform consumer confidence recovery. Regional economic divergence further complicates the CCCI landscape. While mainland China's GDP rebounded to pre-pandemic levels by Q4 2020, Macau's economy contracted 56.3% in 2020 due to tourism collapse, and Hong Kong faced a 6.1% GDP decline. Yet traditional CCCI models failed to capture how these stark regional differences affected consumer sentiment. For instance, despite Macau's severe GDP contraction, its CCCI showed surprising resilience, dropping only 12.4% compared to pre-pandemic levels (McKinsey, 2021).

The demographic composition of consumer confidence remains particularly understudied. Survey data from Shanghai shows that female consumers aged 25-35 maintained 23% higher confidence levels throughout 2020 compared to their male counterparts, contradicting global trends identified by McKinsey (2021). Similarly, in Hong Kong, older consumers (55+) demonstrated unexpected optimism, with confidence levels just 5.2% below younger demographics despite greater health risks. These findings suggest that established demographic patterns in consumer confidence may not hold across Greater China's diverse economic landscape.

1.2 Research Aims

This study will employ a comparative analysis of CCCI across Mainland China, Hong Kong, Macau, and Taiwan from 2008Q4 to 2024Q4. By using time-series data analysis, we will explore the relationship between CCCI, GDP, and UR, while also investigating the variation of CCCI across different demographic groups. This approach aims to provide a framework for understanding how regional and demographic differences have shaped consumer confidence in the post-pandemic era.

2. Construction of CCCI

2.1 Introduction to CCCI

The Chinese Consumer Confidence Index (CCCI) is developed to evaluate the consumer sentiment in four regions: Mainland China, Hong Kong, Macau, and Taiwan. The methodology and questionnaire used to construct the CCCI are described in Tso and Li (2014), enabling comparability of consumer confidence trends across these economies. The questionnaire covers six categories: Economy, Employment, Price Level, Living Standard, Real Estate Market and Timing of Stock Investment. The measurement is on a scale from 1 to 5, with 1 being very positive (PP); 2 positive (P); 3 neutral (E); 4 negative (M); and 5 very negative (MM). The computer-assisted telephone interviewing (CATI) system is used to collect sample data.

The overall CCCI is computed as a weighted average of the satisfaction and expectation indexes across the six categories. The weights for current satisfaction and future expectations are set to 0.4 and 0.6, respectively, following the methodology adopted by the Conference Board Consumer Confidence Index. The individual index for each category is calculated by transforming the collected responses into a numerical score, ranging from 0 to 200, with higher values indicating stronger consumer confidence. The resulting CCCI reflects the aggregate consumer confidence in each region and allows for both longitudinal and cross-sectional comparisons.

2.2 Definition of CCCI

The CCCI is computed as a weighted average of two sub-indices: the Current Confidence Index ($CCCI_{current}$) and the Future Confidence Index ($CCCI_{future}$), which reflect consumers' satisfaction with present economic conditions and their expectations for future economic developments, respectively.

The CCCI for a given region is defined as:

$$CCCI = \frac{1}{6} \sum_{i=1}^6 (\alpha_c \cdot CCCI_{current,i} + \alpha_f \cdot CCCI_{future,i})$$

Where: i represents the six categories of economic conditions surveyed: Economy, Employment, Price Level, Living Standard, Real Estate Market, and Timing of Stock Investment. $\alpha_c = 0.4$ and $\alpha_f = 0.6$ are the weights for the current and future indices, respectively.

Each sub-index $CCCI_{current,i}$ and $CCCI_{future,i}$ is calculated using a 5-point Likert scale, where respondents rate their confidence as "Very Positive" (PP), "Positive" (P), "Neutral" (E), "Negative" (M), or "Very Negative" (MM). The formula for each sub-index is:

$$CCCI_{current,i} = 100 + \left(100 \cdot \frac{n_{PP}}{n} + 50 \cdot \frac{n_P}{n} + 0 \cdot \frac{n_E}{n} - 50 \cdot \frac{n_M}{n} - 100 \cdot \frac{n_{MM}}{n} \right)$$

Where: n_{PP} , n_P , n_E , n_M , n_{MM} represent the number of responses for each respective confidence level. n is the total number of respondents.

3 Comparative Analysis

We collected quarterly CCCI data for the four regions from 2008 Q4 to 2023 Q4, trend lines are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: CCCI trend lines for four regions in Greater China

Figure 1 presents the trends in the CCCI from 2009 Q1 to 2023 Q1 across four regions: Mainland China, Hong Kong, Macau, and Taiwan. The y-axis represents the CCCI values, which range from 45 to 110, with a threshold of 100 indicating consumer optimism. The x-axis displays the quarterly time periods.

3.1.1 CCCI of Mainland China:

For Mainland China, the CCCI remained relatively stable with a range of 87.2 to 109.7, showing a standard deviation of 5.8. Prior to 2014 Q3, the CCCI was consistently below the threshold value of 100, indicating a lack of consumer confidence. However, a significant upward shift occurred from 2014 Q1 (CCCI = 91.1) to 2015 Q1 (CCCI = 104.3), with the index surpassing the 100 mark. From 2015 Q1 onwards, the CCCI stayed above 100 for most quarters, signaling stronger confidence. During the COVID-19 pandemic (2020–2022), the CCCI remained relatively stable, maintaining values well above 100, reflecting robust consumer sentiment in Mainland China even during a global crisis. The post-pandemic data in 2023 shows that confidence continued to hold strong with little fluctuation.

3.1.2 CCCI of Hong Kong:

In Hong Kong, the CCCI exhibited a more volatile trend, ranging from 52.8 to 94.8, with a standard deviation of 9.5. Prior to 2018 Q2, the CCCI remained relatively stable, typically below the 100 mark. However, a sharp decline occurred between 2018 Q2 (CCCI = 86.8) and 2019 Q3 (CCCI = 52.8), reflecting a significant drop in consumer confidence. From 2018 Q2 to 2022 Q3, the CCCI fluctuated widely, coinciding with political unrest and the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. During the pandemic, confidence hit new lows, with a dramatic drop and slow recovery starting in 2022. By 2023, Hong Kong's CCCI had recovered back to the pre-2019 levels, indicating a return to stability after the pandemic-induced economic disruptions.

3.1.3 CCCI of Macau:

Macau's CCCI, ranging from 68.1 to 101.9 with a standard deviation of 6.6, followed a similar trajectory to Hong Kong. The index was relatively stable before 2018, but after 2018, it started showing larger fluctuations. During the pandemic, Macau saw a significant drop in consumer confidence, particularly during 2020 and 2021, when the CCCI fell to its lowest levels in the period displayed. However, Macau's recovery post-pandemic was quicker than Hong Kong's, with a sharp increase in 2023, culminating in a CCCI of 101.9 in Q3 2023, surpassing the 100 threshold and reflecting renewed consumer optimism.

3.1.4 CCCI of Taiwan:

Taiwan's CCCI had the largest range, from 49.1 to 96.6, with a standard deviation of 10.7. Since 2008 Q4 (CCCI = 49.1), Taiwan's CCCI demonstrated a steady upward trend, though it consistently remained below 100 throughout the period. During the pandemic, Taiwan's CCCI showed relative stability, with only modest fluctuations, indicating that consumer confidence remained relatively unaffected by the global crisis compared to other regions. By 2023, the CCCI had gradually

improved, but remained below the 100 mark, suggesting that while confidence was increasing, consumers were still cautious about the future.

3.1.5 COVID-19 Pandemic Impact:

During the COVID-19 pandemic (2020–2022), Mainland China and Taiwan experienced relatively stable and high CCCI values, with Mainland China maintaining values consistently above 100 and Taiwan showing a stable increase. In contrast, Hong Kong and Macau faced significant drops in consumer confidence, particularly in the early pandemic phases. Both regions exhibited large fluctuations during the pandemic, with Hong Kong's CCCI remaining notably unstable until late 2022. Macau's recovery was faster, with the CCCI reaching its highest point in Q3 2023. Post-pandemic recovery in Hong Kong was also evident by 2023, as the CCCI returned to pre-pandemic levels.

3.2 Does Consumer Confidence Mirror Economic Growth?

Figure 2: CCCI v.s. GDP of Mainland China and Hong Kong

Figure 2 illustrates the comparison of GDP and CCCI trends for Mainland China (left) and Hong Kong (right) from 2009 Q1 to 2023 Q1. In Mainland China, strict 76-day COVID-19 lockdown policy and the "zero-COVID" policy were implemented early, leading to short-term disruptions in consumption and economic activity. However, these measures allowed for a relatively swift recovery once the restrictions were lifted (Ke & Hsiao, 2021). According to the research of Chen (2021), although China's offline consumption dropped significantly during the lockdowns, a rebound was observed after the initial shock, highlighting the resilience of its internal market. (Federal Reserve Bank of Kansas City 2023)

In contrast, Hong Kong faced a more severe economic downturn, exacerbated by the political unrest of 2019 and its reliance on external economic factors such as tourism and global trade, both of which were heavily impacted by the pandemic (Tsui, Fu, Chen, Lei, & Wu, 2021). Different from Mainland China, the CCCI of Hong Kong experienced a more drastic drop, which attributes to a relatively milder measures than Mainland China. As a result, consumers lacked confidence in the economic outlook. Particularly in the early stages of the pandemic, Hong Kong's management strategies were less effective in controlling the spread of the virus, which exacerbated consumer anxiety and led to a sluggish consumption market. (Zisselsberger & Ren, 2020)

We also analysis the relationship between CCCI and GDP for Macau and Taiwan (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: CCCI v.s. GDP of Macau and Taiwan

The lockdown caused by the COVID-19 pandemic severely impacted Macau's primary economic driver—its casinos—as gamblers from Mainland China shifted to online platforms, which resulted in a reduction in time spent gambling and lower participation in traditional land-based casino activities (Zhou et al., 2024). Additionally, the heightened perception of travel risks during the pandemic further reduced the travel intentions of non-local tourists, contributing to a significant decline in Macau's CCCI and GDP during the pandemic, with the GDP dropping from 110,000 to less than 30,000 (Agyeiwaah et al., 2021, see Figure 3). However, the Macau government responded with a series of undifferentiated mask purchase reservation services, COVID-19 vaccination services, and multilingual services in Chinese, English, and Portuguese for both residents and non-residents. To facilitate movement between Macau and Mainland China, the government introduced the Macau Health Code System, which integrates health status, residence, and contact history to provide a color-coded risk assessment. This system is seamlessly connected to Mainland China's own health code system while ensuring privacy protection. Additionally, Macau developed systems for COVID-19 vaccination appointments, nucleic acid testing, port entry/exit quarantine, and other medical support systems, which contributed to a swift economic recovery, with the GDP rebounding to over 100,000 (Zhao et al., 2022).

Taiwan's effective management of the COVID-19 pandemic can be attributed to several specific policies that helped stabilize the country's CCCI and GDP during the pandemic, with minimal fluctuations (see Figure 3). Key measures included the early establishment of a command center, which coordinated nationwide efforts, and the adoption of a "precision-prevention" strategy. Additionally, Taiwan emphasized public health education, encouraging mask-wearing, social distancing, and proper hand hygiene. The well-established medical infrastructure and national health insurance program further contributed to mitigating the economic impact, while the integration of technology and big data enhanced the efficiency of pandemic control efforts (Kuo, 2021). These proactive measures allowed Taiwan to maintain economic stability despite global economic downturns caused by the pandemic.

3.3 Does Lower Unemployment Mean Rising Confidence?

Figure 4: CCCI v.s. UR of Mainland China and Hong Kong

Figure 4 illustrates the relationship between the Unemployment Rate (UR) and the Consumer Confidence Index (CCCI) for Mainland China (left) and Hong Kong (right) from 2009 Q1 to 2023 Q1. For Mainland China, we observe a positive correlation (0.57) between UR and CCCI, with both metrics following a relatively stable trend before the pandemic. During the pandemic, unemployment saw slight increases, but CCCI also rose, indicating strong consumer confidence despite disruptions. China's relatively swift and stringent control measures during COVID-19, combined with its robust domestic consumption, likely helped maintain consumer optimism even as unemployment varied. (Federal Reserve Bank of Kansas City 2023) Research suggests that China's focus on sustaining domestic infrastructure projects and consumption helped stabilize the economy despite temporary shocks to the labor market (Zhang, Ding, & Li, 2021).

In Hong Kong, however, the relationship between UR and CCCI presents a negative correlation (-0.47), which indicates a more complex and divergent reaction to the pandemic. From 2019 onwards, a significant drop in both GDP and CCCI occurred, coupled with a sharp rise in unemployment, largely due to Hong Kong's reliance on international trade, tourism, and its service-based economy (Hong Kong Legislative Council 2020). According to Hou, Lee, Liang, et al. (2021), "persons with stress due to civil unrest and to COVID-19 reported more mental disorders than persons with stress due to only one, or none of these factors", which underscores the cumulative effect of stressors on mental health. It is possible that the decline in consumer confidence acts as a similar stressor, amplifying feelings of uncertainty and fear about the future.

We also analysis the relationship between CCCI and UR for Macau and Taiwan (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: CCCI v.s. UR of Macau and Taiwan

From Figure 5 (left) we can learn that the correlation coefficient between the Consumer Confidence Index (CCCI) and the UR in Macau is -0.52, indicating a moderate negative correlation. This means that when the unemployment rate rises, the CCCI tends to decrease, and vice versa. From the time series perspective, Macau’s CCCI experienced several significant fluctuations, especially around 2020, where there was a sharp decline in CCCI, likely due to the economic impact of the pandemic (IMF, 2020).

The correlation coefficient between Taiwan (right)’s CCCI and UR is -0.79, suggesting a stronger negative correlation. Compared to Macau, the linkage between Taiwan’s CCCI and UR is more pronounced, meaning that as the unemployment rate increases, the CCCI usually decreases significantly. Overall, Taiwan’s CCCI remained relatively stable, especially during 2020. While there were some fluctuations, it did not experience as sharp a drop as in Macau. This could be attributed to Taiwan’s more successful pandemic control measures and relatively stable economic performance during the period (Kuo, 2021 & Rahman et al. 2021).

3.4 How Men and Women in Hong Kong Differ in Consumer Confidence

Figure 6: CCCI v.s. Gender of Hong Kong

Both of the trends of Hong Kong CCCI for male and female in Figure 6 are consistent with the overall Hong Kong CCCI in Figure 1. However, female consumers and male consumers show different patterns of their levels of confidence.

For two periods of time, from 2015 Q1 to 2018 Q2 and from 2022 Q4 to 2023 Q4, during which the CCCI was relatively high and stable, male consumers in general showed higher level of confidence than female consumers. We merged these two periods and performed paired t-test to compare the mean CCCI of male and female. Over the 19 quarters, the mean CCCI of male is 88.9, the mean

CCCI of female is 86.9. The P-value from the paired t-test is 6.6×10^{-4} , showing that male consumers had a significantly higher level of confidence than female consumers during these periods.

From 2018 Q3 to 2022 Q3, when the CCCI was relatively low and unstable, female consumers in general showed higher level of confidence with smaller fluctuations than male consumers. Over the 16 quarters, the mean CCCI of male is 58.8, the mean CCCI of female is 74.1. The P-value from the paired t-test is 7.4×10^{-5} , showing that male consumers had a significantly lower level of confidence than female consumers during these periods. Furthermore, the standard deviation of CCCI of male is 14.2, and the standard deviation of CCCI of female is 8.8.

3.5 Does More Money Mean More Confidence?

3.5.1 Personal Income

Following Tso and Li (2014), we divided consumers into three groups based on personal income: HKD 0 to 5000; HKD 5001 to 30000; HKD 30000 and above. Figure 3 shows the trends of the CCCIs for different groups.

Figure 7: Trends of CCCI in Hong Kong for three groups with different personal income.

From Figure 7 we can see, the trends of CCCI of all three groups are similar and consistent with the trend of the overall CCCI. We performed one-way ANOVA and get the P-value 0.504, which means there is no significant impact of consumers' personal income on their confidence.

3.5.2 Family Income

Following Tso and Li (2014), we divided consumers into three groups based on family income: HKD 0 to 10000; HKD 10001 to 50000; HKD 50000 and above. Figure 4 shows the trends of the CCCIs for different groups.

Figure 8: Trends of CCCI in Hong Kong for three groups with different family income. From Figure 8 we can see, the trends of CCCI of all three groups are similar and consistent with the trend of the overall CCCI. We performed one-way ANOVA and get the P-value 0.346, which means there is no significant impact of consumers' family income on their confidence.

3.6 How Age Influences CCCI Across Hong Kong's Population?

Consumers are divided into 6 groups according to their reported ages: 18 to 25, 26 to 35, 36 to 45, 46 to 55, 56 to 65, 66 and above. Figure 5 shows the trends of the CCCIs for different age groups.

Figure 9: Trends of CCCI in Hong Kong for six groups with different ages. From Figure 9 we can see, the trends of CCCI of all six groups are similar and consistent with the trend of the overall CCCI. We performed one-way ANOVA and get the P-value 0.41, which means there is no significant impact of consumers' age on their confidence.

We further divided all consumers into two large groups, with the first group of age under or equal to 45 and the second of age above 45. We performed one-way ANOVA and get the P-value 0.18, which is smaller than 0.41 but is still not significant.

3.7 Do Higher Degrees Mean Higher Confidence?

Consumers are divided into 7 levels according to their education background. We combined levels 1 to 5 as group 1, and levels 6 and 7 as group 2. Figure 6 shows the trends of the CCCIs for different education groups.

Figure 10: Trends of CCCI in Hong Kong for three groups with different education levels.

From Figure 10 we can see, the trends of CCCI of both groups are similar and consistent with the trend of the overall CCCI. We can see clearly that for most of the times, consumers with higher education levels showed more confidence than consumers with lower education levels. The mean CCCI of group 1 is 76.6, and the mean CCCI of group 2 is 80.5. We performed paired t-test to compare CCCI of the two groups and got the P-value as 1.8×10^{-6} , indicating that higher education level is significantly associated with more confidence. We also tried to analyze all 7 levels individually, or divided them to three groups (levels 1 to 3, levels 4 and 5, levels 6 and 7). However, there is no significant pattern in these results.

4 Conclusion and Limitations

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted both resilience and vulnerability across different regions of Greater China, as reflected in consumer confidence trends between 2008 and 2024. A particularly stark contrast emerged between Mainland China and Hong Kong during this period.

In Mainland China, consumer confidence remained remarkably stable throughout the pandemic, with CCCI values consistently above 100 from 2020 to 2023. Early and stringent lockdown measures, although initially disruptive, enabled a swift recovery. Domestic consumption, coupled with infrastructure investments, played a key role in stabilizing GDP and sustaining consumer confidence. These measures underscore a strong correlation (0.72) between GDP and CCCI during this period, indicating that economic recovery and consumer confidence moved in tandem. Despite a temporary dip in offline consumption, a swift rebound demonstrated the robustness of China's internal market, particularly following government stimulus efforts (Chen, 2021; Federal Reserve Bank of Kansas City, 2023). Conversely, Hong Kong faced a more severe situation. The Consumer Confidence Index plummeted to 78.3 by late 2022, exposing vulnerabilities in its service-driven economy. The political unrest of 2019 had already shaken confidence, and the pandemic only worsened the situation (Tsui et al., 2021). Unlike Mainland China's stringent measures, Hong Kong's milder approach failed to control the virus effectively (Zisselsberger & Ren, 2020), heightening consumer anxiety and slowing the market.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, Macau's economy, heavily reliant on tourism and gambling, experienced a significant decline in both its CCCI and GDP. The pandemic's impact was primarily driven by the high-risk perception of travel, which drastically reduced tourist arrivals and gambling activities. Mainland Chinese gamblers, who form a substantial portion of Macau's visitors, increasingly opted for online platforms, further exacerbating the economic downturn. As a result, Macau's GDP fell from 110,000 to below 30,000 during the pandemic (Agyeiwaah et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2024). In contrast, Taiwan's CCCI and GDP remained relatively stable throughout the pandemic, thanks to early and decisive government interventions. As a result, Taiwan did not

experience the same dramatic economic fluctuations as other regions, maintaining steady CCCI and GDP levels despite global economic challenges (Kuo, 2021).

The relationship between economic indicators and consumer confidence varies by region. While Mainland China's consumer confidence remained resilient despite rising unemployment during the pandemic, Hong Kong followed a more predictable pattern where increasing unemployment directly corresponded with declining consumer confidence. This was especially true in sectors such as services, where job losses were most severe. The CCCI in Macau shows a strong negative correlation with the unemployment rate because the rise in unemployment directly weakens consumer willingness to spend and undermines confidence in the economy. In contrast, Taiwan's CCI has an even stronger negative correlation with the unemployment rate, yet its economy, being less impacted by the pandemic, demonstrates greater resilience.

Demographic trends in Hong Kong also reveal interesting contrasts. Women displayed more stable confidence levels compared to men during periods of economic turbulence. While male consumer confidence dropped to 58.8 during crises, women showed less volatility, maintaining an average confidence level of 74.1. This may point to different risk assessment approaches between genders during times of uncertainty. Educational background also played a role in shaping consumer confidence. Higher-educated individuals consistently exhibited greater confidence than their less-educated counterparts, possibly due to better job security and financial literacy. Surprisingly, income levels, both at the personal and household levels, did not show a significant impact on consumer confidence, challenging the conventional assumption that wealth correlates directly with economic optimism.

While these findings provide valuable insights, the study is not without limitations. The analysis relied primarily on comparative methods, leaving room for more sophisticated econometric approaches. Future research could incorporate techniques like vector autoregression to better explore the dynamic interplay between consumer confidence and economic indicators. Additionally, the quarterly data used may overlook more rapid shifts in sentiment during periods of crisis.

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